

Article

First Report of Phoresy of the Genus *Lophochernes* Simon, 1878 (Pseudoscorpiones: Chernetidae) on the Cerambycid Beetle *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775)

APARNA SURESHCHANDRA KALAWATE^{1*}, POOJA KUMAR MISAL² AND THAPASYA K¹

¹Zoological Survey of India, Western Regional Centre, Vidya Nagar, Sector-29, P.C.N.T (PO), Rawet Road, Akurdi, Pune, Maharashtra 411044, India.

Email: devarpanento@gmail.com; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6595-6749>

Email: thapasya.k@zsi.gov.in; thapasya1444@gmail.com; <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1396-4604>

²PhD Scholar, Shivaji University, Vidyanagar, Kolhapur - 416 004. Maharashtra, India Email: pkmspider@gmail.com;

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3336-7904>

*Corresponding author: Email: devarpanento@gmail.com; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6595-6749>

Abstract

Pseudoscorpions are well known for their phoretic associations with various arthropods. In the present study, a phoretic association of *Lophochernes* sp. (Pseudoscorpiones: Chernetidae) with the cerambycid beetle *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775) is reported for the first time. This observation extends the known host range of pseudoscorpion phoresy and highlights the need for further studies on their phoretic interactions with other arthropod taxa.

Key words: Phorecy, Pseudoscorpiones, beetle, arthropod dispersal, mango-stem borer.

Introduction

Phoresy represents a specialized ecological interaction in which one organism, termed the *phoront*, attaches to another organism (the host) primarily for transportation or dispersal. This association is generally non-parasitic and commensal in nature, serving as an adaptive mechanism that enables small and weakly mobile invertebrates to expand their distribution across diverse arthropod taxa (Croker, 1975; Norton, 1987; Poinar *et al.*, 1998; White *et al.*, 2017; Rueda *et al.*, 2021; Mahunlik *et al.*, 2022). Two principal forms of phoresy are recognized among arthropods: active phoresy, wherein the phoront deliberately attaches to an external body region of the host, and passive phoresy, in which the phoront occupies a protected site such as a cavity or structural recess on or within the host's body (Vachon, 1954; Athias-Binche, 1994).

Pseudoscorpions are minute arachnids, typically measuring between 0.7–12 mm in length. They are widely distributed and inhabit microhabitats such as bark crevices, beneath stones, leaf litter, and decomposing wood. Due to their small size and limited dispersal capability, pseudoscorpions rely extensively on phoresy as an effective strategy for colonization. This behavior facilitates access to new habitats while minimizing risks associated with desiccation, predation, and local resource depletion (Muchmore, 2000; Harvey, 2003). Phoretic behavior in pseudoscorpions generally occurs during the non-feeding deutonymph stage, during which individuals actively seek suitable hosts and attach using their pedipalpal chelae. Upon reaching favorable environments rich in potential prey such as collembolans and other microarthropods, they detach to establish new populations (Poinar *et al.*, 1998).

The known range of phoretic hosts for pseudoscorpions is broad, encompassing several insect orders including Diptera, Hymenoptera, Lepidoptera, and small Coleoptera (Aguiar & Bührnheim, 1998; Poinar *et al.*, 1998; Aguiar & Bührnheim, 2010; Rueda *et al.*, 2021; Harvey *et al.*, 2021). Among

Coleoptera, wood-boring families such as Cerambycidae and Passalidae are particularly well-documented hosts. In cerambycids, it was not documented on *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775).

The longhorn beetle *B. rufomaculata*, commonly known as the mango stem borer, is a highly destructive polyphagous pest of several economically important trees, notably *Mangifera indica* L. and *Ficus carica* L. Its larvae bore deep tunnels through the heartwood and sapwood of trunks and major branches, disrupting vascular tissues and causing wilting, dieback, and, in severe cases, tree mortality, leading to significant economic losses (Mitra, 2013). Reports indicate that infestation intensity varies greatly, with damage ranging from approximately 5% to over 50% in heavily infested orchards (Chavan *et al.*, 2025; Maldonado-Pindo *et al.*, 2025).

Although phoresy involving pseudoscorpions, particularly those belonging to the families Chernetidae and Cheliferidae, has been documented on various beetles, reports of such associations with large-sized cerambycids are rare. Here, we present the first record of a phoretic association between the genus *Lophochernes* Simon, 1878 and the cerambycid beetle *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775). This finding expands the known range of pseudoscorpion hosts and contributes to our understanding of the ecological versatility of phoretic relationships in this group. Here we present a first report of phoresy of *Lophochernes* sp. on *B. rufomaculata*.

Materials and Methods

Specimens were collected during a faunal survey conducted at the Shendi Rest House area, Kalsubai–Harishchandragad Wildlife Sanctuary, Maharashtra (Figure 1 and 2). A light trap was installed at the site to attract nocturnal insects as part of routine sampling (Figure 2). During sorting of the collected material, a cerambycid beetle specimen was recovered, which upon close examination under a hand lens was found to bear attached pseudoscorpions on its legs (Figure 4A and B).

Figure 1. Map of collection locality of *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775) and *Lophochernes* sp. from Kalsubai-Harishchandragad Wildlife Sanctuary.

Figure 2. Habitat from where *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775) and *Lophochernes* sp. were collected: (A) near Bhandardara dam where the light trap was installed, (B) light trap.

The attached pseudoscorpions were carefully removed using a fine, soft-bristled brush to avoid damage and were preserved for further examination and documentation. Both the beetle and the pseudoscorpions were identified based on external morphology and diagnostic characters using available taxonomic keys and relevant literature (Batuwita & Benjamin, 2014; Gahan, 1906, etc.).

Pseudoscorpion specimens were studied under a Leica S9i stereozoom microscope equipped with an inbuilt photographic facility. Field photographs of *B. rufomaculata* specimens and the study site were taken using a Nikon Coolpix P1000 camera. The map of the collection locality was generated using QGIS software version 3.22.7 (Open-Source Geospatial Foundation Project) (Figure 1).

Results

The cerambycid beetle was identified as *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775) (Figure 3), while the attached pseudoscorpion was identified up to the genus level as *Lophochernes* sp. (Figure 4C), following Batuwita and Benjamin (2014).

The pseudoscorpion was observed firmly clasping the tarsal segments of the beetle's leg using its pedipalpal chelae (Figure 4A and B). Importantly, the chelae were not inserted into or damaging the host's integument, thereby confirming the interaction as phoretic rather than parasitic in nature. The positioning

of the pseudoscorpion on the tarsal region suggests a secure attachment site that facilitates transport while minimizing interference with the host's movement.

Figure 3. Adult Habitus of *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775).

Figure 4. A and B. *Lophochernes* sp. attached to the tarsal segments of *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775) in red circle, C. Dorsal habitus of *Lophochernes* sp.

1) Identification of host

Order: Coleoptera (Linnaeus, 1758)
 Superfamily: Chrysomeloidea (Latreille, 1802)
 Family: Cerambycidae (Latreille, 1802)
 Subfamily: Lamiinae (Latreille, 1825)
 Tribe: Batocerini (Thomson, 1864)
 Genus *Batocera* (Dejean, 1835)

***Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775)** (Figure 3).

Material examined: 01ex, Shendi rest house, Kalsubai-Harishchandragad Wildlife Sanctuary, Maharashtra, 07.viii.2024, A.S. Kalawate & party (ZSI-WRC-Ent-1/4936).

2) Identification of phoront

Phylum: Arthropoda (Latreille, 1829)
 Subphylum: Chelicerata (Heymons, 1901)
 Class: Arachnida (Lamarck, 1801)
 Order: Pseudoscorpiones (De Geer, 1778)
 Superfamily: Cheliferoidea (Risso, 1826)
 Family: Chernetidae (Menge, 1855)
 Subfamily: Chernetinae (Menge, 1855)
 Genus *Lophochernes* (Simon, 1878)

Lophochernes sp. (Figure 4)

Material examined: 03ex, Shendi rest house, Kalsubai-Harishchandragad Wildlife Sanctuary, Maharashtra, 07.viii.2024, A.S. Kalawate & party (ZSI, WRC, Misc./ 21).

Discussion

Phoresy involving large-bodied beetles is likely underreported, primarily because pseudoscorpions often attach to concealed or cryptic regions of the host's body and may remain associated only for short periods. Utilizing large beetles as phoretic hosts offers pseudoscorpions distinct advantages, as these insects possess strong flight capabilities and can cover considerable distances. Such hosts, therefore, serve as efficient dispersal vectors, enabling pseudoscorpions to colonize new habitats that would otherwise be inaccessible to them.

Recent studies have broadened our understanding of these associations by documenting phoretic relationships involving different *Batocera* species. For instance, *Lophochernes bicarinatus* Simon, 1878 has been recorded on *Batocera davidis* Fairmaire, 1878 in Taiwan (Lin and Liu, 2020), and *Lissochelifer superbus* (With, 1906) has been reported on *Batocera celebiana* Thomson, 1858 (Beier, 1948; Poinar *et al.*, 1998). These findings suggest that large cerambycid beetles may play an important yet overlooked role in the dispersal ecology of pseudoscorpions.

Phoresy in pseudoscorpions represents a key ecological adaptation that promotes population connectivity, facilitates gene flow, and contributes to the persistence of species in fragmented or isolated habitats. The present study provides the first record of a phoretic association between a pseudoscorpion and a cerambycid beetle from India. The discovery of *Lophochernes* sp. on *B. rufomaculata* expands the known host range of pseudoscorpions and emphasizes the ecological flexibility of phoretic interactions in this group.

This observation adds to the growing body of evidence that pseudoscorpions engage in diverse and complex phoretic relationships with a wide range of arthropod hosts. Further studies integrating field surveys, behavioral observations, and molecular approaches are needed to clarify the frequency, host specificity, and evolutionary implications of these associations, as well as their potential influence on the population dynamics and ecological strategies of both the phoront and its beetle host.

Acknowledgements

Authors are grateful to the Director, Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata and the Officer-in-Charge, Zoological Survey of India, Western Regional Centre, Pune for constant encouragement and research facilities. Authors are thankful to the reviewer's and the subject editor for their valuable suggestions and constructive criticism that improved the manuscript. Due acknowledgments to the Maharashtra Forest Department for permission and permit & logistic support during the survey.

References

- Aguiar, N.O., & Bührnheim, P.F. 1998. Phoretic pseudoscorpions associated with flying insects in Brazilian Amazônia. *Journal of Arachnology*, 26(3), 452–459.
- Aguiar, N.O., & Bührnheim, P.F. 2010. Dispersão por forésia de pseudoscorpionídeos associados a insetos, na província de Uruçu (Coari, Amazonas, Brasil). In: Castellón Bermúdez, E.G., Ronchi-Teles, B. and Ale-Rocha, R (eds). *Entomologia na Amazônia Brasileira. Manaus*, Brazil, pp. 53–78.
- Athias-binche, F. 1994. La phorésie chez les acaríens. Aspects adaptatifs et évolutifs. Perpignan, Paris, France: Edition dus Castillet, 178 pp.
- Batuwita, S., & Benjamin, S. 2014. An annotated checklist and a family key to the pseudoscorpion fauna (Arachnida: Pseudoscorpiones) of Sri Lanka. *Zootaxa*, 3814, 37–67.
- Beier, M. 1948. Phoresie und Phagophilie bei Pseudoscorpionen. *Österreichische zoologische Zeitschrift*, 1(5): 441–497.

- Chavan, S.M., P.V.R. Reddy, P. Srivastava, G.S. Naik, S. Kaur, S.R. Singh, H.L. Devi, S. Singh, S. Singh, C.S. Maiti, A. Kar, V.K. Rana S.S. Kanna, R.S. Kadu, A. Kumar, C. Kushwaha, N. Akkabathula, S.S. Lakhawat, A.Y. Munj, J.K. Bana, P. Patil and S., & Priya D. 2025. Management of mango stem borer, *Batocera rufomaculata* De Geer by using 'Arka Borer Control'- A multi-location study. *Journal of Environmental Biology*, 46, 611–624.
- Crocker, R.A. 1975. Phoresy: A review. *Entomophaga*, 20(3), 233–242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02372024>
- Gahan, C.J. 1906. The fauna of British India including Ceylon and Burma: Coleoptera: Cerambycidae Volume 1. Bingham C. T. (Ed). Taylor and Francis, London, pp. 329.
- Harvey, M.S., Woolf, M., Beattie, M., & Bassett, S. 2021. The first definitive case of phoresy of a pseudoscorpion on a carabid beetle (Coleoptera: Carabidae). *Australian Entomologist*, 48(3), 145–150.
- Harvey, M.S. 2003. The smaller the better: patterns of phoresy in pseudoscorpions. In: Bernasconi, G. et al. (Eds.), *Experimental Approaches to Conservation Biology*. University of California Press, 1–24.
- Lin, H-Y., & Liu, H-H. 2020. First record of a phoretic relationship between *Lophochernes bicarinatus* (Pseudoscorpionida: Cheliferidae) and *Batocera davidis* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in Taiwan. *Taiwan Journal of Biodiversity*, 22, 63–68.
- Maldonado-Pinto, N. M., Cabrera-Asencio, I., & Harmsen, E.W. 2025. *Batocera rufomaculata* (De Geer, 1775) (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae): Incidence, severity and preference for *Mangifera indica* cultivars. *The Journal of Agriculture of the University of Puerto Rico*, 109(1), 155–184. <https://doi.org/10.46429/jaupr.v109i1.22218>
- Mahunlik, C., Stary, P., & Zrzavý, J. 2022. Evolution of phoresy in nematodes and arthropods: a phylogenetic perspective. *Biological Reviews*, 97(2), 502–520. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12811>
- Mitra, B. 2013. New records of longicorn beetle borers (Lamiinae: Cerambycidae: Coleoptera) from Little Nicobar Island, Indian Ocean. *Journal of the Andaman Science Association*, 18(1), 123–124.
- Muchmore, W.B. 2000. Phoretic associations of pseudoscorpions. In: Selden, P.A. (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 17th European Colloquium of Arachnology*. British Arachnological Society, pp. 123–128.
- Norton, R.A. 1987. Coevolution of phoretic mites and their insect hosts. *Evolutionary Biology*, 21, 233–290. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4684-5310-7_6
- Poinar Jr., G.O., Curcic, B.P.M., & Cokendolpher, J.C. 1998. Arthropod phoresy involving pseudoscorpions in the past and present. *Acta Arachnologica*, 47(2), 79–96.
- Poinar, G.O., Čurčić, B.P.M., & Sretović, B. 1998. Phoresy of pseudoscorpions on beetles (Coleoptera) from Dominican amber. Mededelingen van de Faculteit Landbouwkundige en Toegepaste Biologische Wetenschappen, *Universiteit Gent*, 63(2), 567–571.
- Rueda-Ramírez, D.E., García, L.F., & Wolff, M. 2021. Phoresy in pseudoscorpions: diversity, mechanisms, and ecological significance. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 191(3), 826–850. <https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnea/zlaa059>
- Vachon, M., 1954. Nouvelles captures de Pseudoscorpions (Arachnides) transportés par des insectes. *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris*, 2(2), 590–592.
- White, P.S., Morran, L.T., & de Roode, J.C. 2017. Phoresy. *Current Biology*, 27(12), R578–R580.